

Local and Global Strain and Defect Analysis of Discontinuous Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymers

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Motivation

1. **Material Development** (microscale analysis \Leftrightarrow FE simulations)
2. **Application development** (experiments on the macroscale \Leftrightarrow component design)

Motivation

Short glass fibres (PPSGF)

nominal fibre diameter **13 μm**
mean fibre length approx. **470 μm**

Long glass fibres (PPLGF)

nominal fibre diameter **17 μm**
mean fibre length approx. **1000 μm**

- Highly oriented
- Skin/shell/core layers
- Curved fibres
- Fibre bundles
- Local differences in fibre content

What differences arise in the defect behaviour?

Motivation

What differences in the strain formation and distribution with regard to fibre structure, fibre orientation and specimen geometry can be identified?

Materials & Methods

- **Two different materials:**
 - **Polypropylene with 24 wt.% short glass fibres (PPSGF):**
nominal fibre diameter 13 μm , mean fibre length approx. 470 μm
 - **Polypropylene with 24 wt.% long glass fibres (PPLGF):**
nominal fibre diameter 17 μm , mean fibre length approx. 1000 μm
- **Two different specimen geometries (CR – constant radius, DENT – double edge notched)**
cut out from injection moulded GF-Multitool at **three different orientations**

Materials & Methods

Interrupted in situ tensile testing

CT data acquisition:

- Voxel edge length:
PPSGF 2 μm
PPLGF 2.5 μm
- Scan time: ~ 1h
- Voltage: 80 kV
- Current: 400 μA

Load step definition:

- Based on the maximum tensile force evaluated with pre-evaluations
- starting at 30% followed by 52% and increasing in 8% steps until fracture

Materials & Methods

CT-data evaluation

Strain analysis

DVC tool, Avizo Software 2020.1

Displacement vector
Strain tensor
Volumetric strain
Poisson's ratio
Prediction of fracture surface

Defect analysis

Amirkhanov et al. (2016), Rao et al. (2017), Maurer et al. (2019)

Defect type
Defect number
Defect size
Defect formation

Results

PPSGF - CR 0°
LS 7 – 92 % of $F_{max 0°}$

PPSGF - CR 90°
LS 6 – 84 % of $F_{max 90°}$

PPSGF - CR 45°
LS 5 – 76 % of $F_{max 45°}$

500 μ m

**Defects at
LAST
load step before fracture**

- matrix fracture
- fibre-matrix debonding
- fibre pull-out
- fibre fracture

**Matrix fracture
dominating**

**Distribution of
defect types
due to local
fibre
orientation**

Results

PPSGF - CR 0°
 LS 7 – 92 % of $F_{max\ 0°}$

PPSGF - CR 90°
 LS 6 – 84 % of $F_{max\ 90°}$

PPSGF - CR 45°
 LS 5 – 76 % of $F_{max\ 45°}$

500 μ m

Defects and strain at LAST load step before fracture

- matrix fracture
- fibre-matrix debonding
- fibre pull-out
- fibre fracture

Local strain hotspots indicating positions of fracture onset and correlate well with defect hotspots

Results

PPLGF - CR 0°
LS 5 – 76 % of $F_{\max 0^\circ}$

PPLGF - CR 90°
LS 4 – 68 % of $F_{\max 90^\circ}$

PPLGF - CR 45°
LS 5 – 76 % of $F_{\max 45^\circ}$

500 μm

**Defects and strain at
LAST
load step before fracture**

- matrix fracture
- fibre-matrix debonding
- fibre pull-out
- fibre fracture

**Less defects and
smaller strain values
for all orientations**

Results

PPLGF - CR 0°
LS 5 – 76 % of $F_{max 0°}$

fracture not necessarily at smallest cross section

no strain hot spots at first load step

local microstructure significantly influence onset of fracture

■ Indicating the fracture surface respectively one fragment of the tested specimen

Results

Strain along a line profile at the smallest cross section and the center of the specimen

Shape of the strain distribution already apparent at first load step

Strong influence of the notch

Results

Strain analysis of the total volume – comparison of specimen geometry

**plane strain state
due to bigger width than height**

Results

Strain analysis of the total volume – comparison of main fibre orientation

Poisson's ratio $\nu = -\frac{\epsilon_{trans}}{\epsilon_{axial}}$

strain perpendicular to direction of load

strain in direction of load

anisotropic material

$$\nu_{XZ} = -\frac{\epsilon_{XX}}{\epsilon_{ZZ}}$$

$$\nu_{YZ} = -\frac{\epsilon_{YY}}{\epsilon_{ZZ}}$$

strong dependence on main fibre orientation

Results

Comparison of different
stress and strain states

Conclusion

- Short fibre reinforced polypropylene:
 - Defect formation and defect type depend on fibre orientation
 - Major reason for ultimate failure: matrix fracture
- Long glass fibre reinforced polypropylene:
 - No clear correlation between fibre orientation and defect type
 - Strong influence of the strength on the local microstructure (fibre bundles, curved fibres, ...)
 - More quasi-isotropic behavior
- Mechanics (induced by sample geometry) overrule microstructure
- Gained results enable better understanding and (in certain cases) a prediction of the damage behaviour from a 3-dimensional perspective

Thank you!

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